

Impact Of Advertisements On Fashion Adoption Behaviour Of College Students

FASHION

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INTRODUCTION

All of us are consumers. We buy the products and services according to our needs, preferences and buying power. The marketers therefore try to understand the needs of different consumers and having understood their different behaviours formulate their plan for marketing. The process of buying starts in the mind of consumer. Consumer behaviour is a complex, dynamic, multidimensional process. So to understand the likes and dislikes of a consumer, extensive consumer research studies are being conducted. These researches try to find out what the consumer thinks of the company's products, how can the product be improved in their opinion, what is the consumer's attitude towards the product and its advertising, etc.

Advertising can be defined as any form of paid communication with the purpose of motivating a reader or viewer to purchase a product or service, to influence

public opinion, to win political support, to sell an idea or a cause, or to act or think and perhaps influence others in the manner desired by the client. Among the media used to accomplish this are radio, television, newspapers, magazines, direct mail, billboards, posters, catalogues and brochures. Fashion is a style or styles most popular at a given time. A fashion advertisement is a source of changing the attitude of the consumers, so that it becomes favourable towards the company's products.

When we talk about the marketing of a fashion product, its advertisement through an appropriate media is very - very important. Young students are the main consumers of fashion, as they are the ones who are always keen to look for and buy new fashion. So, it is very necessary to find out the most popular advertising media among these potential customers of fashion products. This will help the manufacturers to find out the right way for their goal. Also there are some special features of advertisements on which consumer's pay more attention for example colourful visualization, theme of advertisement, inclusion of celebrity and fashion model, use of sentiments of target group etc. If manufacturers are able to incorporate these features in their product's advertisement it leads to the rapid sale of the fashion product.

When students buy a fashion product there are many factors which affect their behaviour for purchasing a fashion item. Influences of peer group, culture, brand image of product, price, competitive fashion products etc. are the factors that affect the buying behaviour of consumers. Fashion advertisements try their level best to motivate their consumers. Therefore, through this research study, we could get real information as to whether the purchasing behaviour of the college students regarding fashion goods is really influenced by advertisements. To give answer to all these questions, the present study was carried out with the following objectives:

Abstract: When we talk about the marketing of a fashion product, its advertisement through an appropriate media is very -very important. Young boys and girls are the main consumers of fashion, as they are the ones who are always keen to look for and buy new fashion products. So, it is very necessary to find out the most popular advertising media among these potential customers of fashion products. This will help the manufacturers to find out the right way for their goal. When students buy a fashion product there are many factors which affect their behaviour for purchasing a fashion item. Influences of peer group, culture, brand image of product, price, competitive fashion products etc. are the factors that affect the buying behaviour of consumers. Fashion advertisements are a great source of providing information about new fashion product and motivating consumers to buy them.

Key Words: Consumers, fashion advertising media, fashion adoption behaviour, role of fashion advertisements.

1. To find out the most popular advertising media among students.
2. To find out the features of fashion advertisements on which student pay more attention
3. To study the fashion product buying behaviour of college going girls and boys

METHODOLOGY

Study was conducted in the university campus of Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar situated in the state of Uttarakhand. Students pursuing the undergraduate level study at different colleges were selected for collection of data. These colleges were: College of Agriculture, College of Home-Science and College of Technology. A total of 30 college going girls and 30 boys constituting a sample of 60 respondents were selected randomly.

Only the under graduate students were taken for this study because these students are in the age of early adolescence, are frequent users of fashion products as well as recurrent viewer of fashion advertisements through different media. These students have passion to be accepted by their friends and society and try to live trendy.

A questionnaire was developed for data collection and divided into three sections- The first section of questionnaire dealt with background information of the respondents and their family (name, age, education, and family occupation) whereas, the second section consisted of some specific questions related to the features of fashion advertisements from which students are most attracted. The data were collected separately for girls and boys. The third section dealt with the psychological impact of fashion advertisements on the fashion adoption behaviour of students. The content validity of the questionnaire was tested by a panel of judges including five experts in the field of fashion and communication from the department of communication and department of clothing and textiles of Pantnagar University.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Respondent's preferences for different fashion advertising media

Advertising media	Girl's Preference N= (30)		Boy's Preference N= (30)	
	f	Rank	f	Rank
Fashion magazines	20	II	21	II
Women's magazines	20	II	8	V
Men's magazines	5	V	3	VI
Newspaper	15	III	13	IV
Television	23	I	23	I
Internet	8	IV	15	III
Any other (specify)	0	-	1	VII

Table 1 refers to the preferences of the respondents for different fashion advertising media. It is evident from table 1 that television was most preferred fashion advertising media by girls and boys as it got I rank. The second preferred fashion advertising media by girls were both fashion magazines and women's magazine, while in case of boys, they preferred fashion magazine as II preferred media. In the case of boys, internet was selected as III preferred fashion advertising media.

Television is the most preferred media by girls and boys as a source of fashion advertising media. Students prefer it most as according to them television is most easily accessible, readily available and it is most popular among people. Some students say that it is direct source of awareness. We can get more information at no cost. Also one could have a close view and updated information of the Fashion products on television.

T.V. has the biggest impact on awareness of advertising. It gives broad awareness of fashion ads in women's and men's glossies. ([www. marketresearch.com](http://www.marketresearch.com), 2008). According to Fringe (1999), television advertising is growing in popularity as the general public is watching more and reading less. The medium also offers the advantage of being able to show how clothing might fit into real-life situation.

Fashion magazine got rank II by the college students. The reasons for selecting fashion magazine were its attractiveness, popularity and being a modern age media. Students can see the latest trends related to fashion products, it gives the complete description of the products, tells about variety of products, available at affordable price and is very effective. The students said that fashion magazines give ideas and innovations in dress designing and give knowledge of global brands. Fashion magazines have a unique way of presentation; at a glance one can have an idea of the fashion product. Some girls like fashion magazines more than any other media as they give them solution of some problems, for example skin related problems. "Femina", "Elle" and "Cosmopolitan" were the most popular fashion magazines among students.

Women's magazines got overall rank III because of its easy availability, giving complete and correct information about the products, cover wide variety of topics and come under buying capacity of peoples. Some students also said that women's magazines have beautiful and attractive look and give information about the current trend. The popular women's magazines identified among students were "Women's Era", "New Women", "Grahshobha", "Sakhi", "Grahlakshmi" etc. English newspapers like The Times of India and The Hindu also got overall rank III because of their easy accessibility;

they were read daily and were affordable at no extra money needed to spend on fashion advertisements. It is also most acceptable media for students. Internet was also preferred by many boys and girls because students spend more time on internet, it is easily accessible, give latest and attractive information about fashion products. Some students refer internet, because it is a modern age media. Men's magazines were least popular among students may be due to their less accessibility and acceptability among the boys in Pantnagar.

Table 2 Use of advertisements by the respondents for buying various fashion products

Fashion products	GIRLS N= (30)		BOYS N= (30)		OVERALL N= (60)			Rank
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Clothing	18	60	22	73.3	40	66.6		I
Cosmetics	24	80	18	50	34	56.6		II
Jewelry	9	30	4	13.3	13	21.6		V
Garment accessories	12	40	8	26.6	20	33.3		IV
Footwear	14	46.6	20	66.6	34	56.6		II

The table 2 shows that in case of girls (80 %), cosmetics are the fashion products for buying of which they consider advertisements at most of the time. 60 % girls consider fashion advertisements at the time of buying clothing and 46.6 % at the time of buying footwear. In case of boys, 73.3 % boys consider fashion advertisements at the time of buying clothing and 66.6 % boys for buying footwear. It can be concluded that clothing got I rank among girls and boys as in case of buying clothing advertisements are most commonly considered followed by footwear which got rank II. Jewellery is the least preferred fashion products for which students consider advertisements.

The impact of fashion advertisements can be seen when some students said that they buy "Globas" products as they like its advertisements. Some students consider advertisements of jewellery as according to them beautiful designs are there. When most of the students buy clothing, they remember the advertisements in context of new fabrics, new designs and brands of clothing. For example some girls like "Lifestyles" products as these are youthful as depicted by its advertisement. According to *Fringe (1999)*, brands are the manufacturer's means of product identification. Some consumers buy on the basis of a particular brand's reputation, often as a result of heavy advertising.

Table 3 Features of fashion advertisements that seek attention of students.

Sl No	Statements	Students (N=60)	SA (%)	A (%)	CS (%)	DA (%)	SD (%)
1	• Frequently viewed advertisements always seek attention of the viewers	Girls Boy	26.7 40	66.7 53.3	3.3 3.3	3.3 3.3	0 0
2	• Advertisements which are on front pages of any magazine/newspaper are more effective than advertisements on inside pages	Girls Boy	30 30	46.7 43.3	16.7 16.7	6.7 10	0 0
3	• Advertisements with less words are more effective	Girls Boy	23.3 26.7	53.3 33.3	10 16.7	13.3 20	0 3.3
4	• Advertisements on glossy paper with striking colours are more eye catchy than on regular paper	Girls Boy	43.3 33.3	50 36.7	6.7 10	0 16.7	0 3.3
5	• Use of non verbal communication in fashion advertisement is more effective than verbal communication	Girls Boy	26.7 23.3	40 36.7	23.3 20	10 16.7	0 3.3
6	• Use of sentiments of target groups make the advertisements more interesting	Girls Boy	33.3 20	46.7 43.3	10 10	6.7 20	3.3 6.7
7	• Advertisement theme is totally responsible for attracting consumers	Girls Boy	36.7 23.3	28.7 53.3	16.7 6.7	16.7 10	0 6.7
8	• It is essential to change the theme of advertisement frequently	Girls Boy	16.7 43.3	53.3 43.3	20 6.7	10 3.3	0 0
9	• Availability/ local advertisement of the product affects the sale of fashion products	Girls Boy	26.7 26.7	66.7 56.7	6.7 6.7	0 6.7	0 0
10	• Advertisement which introduces the fashion items with special offer attracts more	Girls Boy	23.3 23.3	63.3 40	6.7 26.7	6.7 10	0 6.7
11	• Inclusion of celebrity in advertisement prop up the fashion item	Girls Boy	56.7 56.7	40 16.7	3.3 20	0 3.3	0 0
12	• Brand name plays a vital role in fashion product promotion	Girls Boy	60 46.7	33.3 33.3	6.7 6.7	3.3 0	0 3.3
13	• Model's chic in fashion advertisements really promote the products	Girls Boy	20 33.3	56.7 33.3	20 30	3.3 10	0 0

Table 3 envisaged that 66.7% girls and 53.3% boys agreed that frequently viewed advertisements always seek attention of the viewer, while 3.3% of both girls and boys disagreed with this statement. 30% of both girls and boys strongly agreed, followed by 46.7% girls and 40.3% boys agreed with the statement that advertisements which are on front pages of any magazine/ newspaper are more effective than advertisements on inside pages. Advertisements with fewer words are more effective, this statement was strongly accepted by 23.3% of girls and 26.7% of boys, while 13.3% girls and 20% boys totally disagreed with the statement.

Advertisements on glossy paper with striking colours are more eye catchy than on regular paper as decided by 50 % girls and 36.7 % boys, whereas 16.7% and 3.3% boys disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. 33.3% girls and 20% boys strongly agreed upon the statement that use of sentiments of target groups make the advertisements more interesting, this was followed by 46.7 % girls and 43.3 % boys which were agreed with the same.

Most of the respondents were satisfied with the statement that advertisement theme is totally

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responsible for attracting consumers and it is essential to change the theme of advertisement quite often. It was observed that maximum percentage of respondent i.e. 63.3% of girls and 40% of boys approved that advertisements which introduces the fashion items with special offer attract more. Whereas the percentage of boys (10%) who disagreed with this was more than the percentage of girls which was only 6.7%.

Hamburger, (1976) stated that the message in media comes alive by means of the medium. The most alive message is the changing, exciting, tempting message of fashion, in the living language of eye-language. It is communicated by pictures that have a vocabulary of sight. The eye grasps, understands and translates what it sees into desire. The fashion language of the eye is defined by the vocabulary of the word, the word that informs and persuades. Together they communicate and motivate by means of the media.

A common trend i.e. most of the respondents were strongly agreed and agreed with these two statements viz. inclusion of celebrity in advertisement prop up the fashion item and brand name plays vital role in fashion product promotion. According to Loudon and Bitta (2006), in addition to the brand image, their company's image can strongly influence consumers' behaviour towards their enterprise and its products. A strong and clear company image can increase consumers' confidence in its products and their predisposition to purchase them.

In case of the statement that the model's chic in fashion advertisements really promotes the products, 56.7% of girls and 33.3% boys agreed, but 10% of boys did not agree with the statement. Depicted by this study that some girls buy the fashion products as they are influenced with the chic.

Table 4 Influence of fashion advertisements on fashion items purchasing behaviour of students

Sl. No	Statements	Students (N=30)	SA (%)	A (%)	CS (%)	DA (%)	SD (%)
1	• We buy the things which are used by our peer group	Girls	6.7	70	3.3	20	0
		Boys	20	36.7	30	10	3.3
2	• We buy those fashion items which are endorsed by some celebrity/role model	Girls	10	43.3	13.3	33.3	0
		Boys	20	43.3	10	23.3	3.3
3	• Generally we prefer the fashion products which offer better quality in low price	Girls	40	50	6.7	3.3	0
		Boys	33.3	43.3	10	6.7	6.7
4	• We always buy the products of familiar brand even if there are other options with same features	Girls	36.7	43.3	3.3	16.7	0
		Boys	23.3	36.7	26.7	6.7	6.7
5	• We consider cultural compatibility of the fashion item before buying it	Girls	13.3	66.7	13.3	6.7	0
		Boys	16.7	46.7	16.7	10	10
6	• We try a new product when it comes with some offer	Girls	16.7	40	10	30	3.3
		Boys	23.3	33.3	13.3	26.7	3.3
7	• Buying the fashion items when they are on sale is more economical	Girls	20	60	10	10	0
		Boys	23.3	56.7	10	6.7	3.3
8	• Quality of fashion items on sale is always reliable	Girls	6.7	6.7	30	56.7	0
		Boys	10	23.3	26.7	30	10
9	• High quality fashion products are at high price	Girls	23.3	46.7	13.3	13.3	3.3
		Boys	43.3	23.3	13.3	20	0
10	• Branded fashion products are symbol of our status	Girls	16.7	46.7	3.3	30	3.3
		Boys	36.7	26.7	16.7	6.7	13.3
11	• We are glad to buy the products which we see in TV, serials and movies	Girls	10	63.3	13.3	10	3.3
		Boys	20	36.7	16.7	16.7	10

It is evident from the Table 4 that 70% girls and 36.7% boys agreed that they buy the things which are used by their peer group while 20% and 10% girls and boys respectively disagreed with the statement. According to Fringe (1999), average Americans have conservative tastes; they do not want to differ from their peers. They may want peers to accept them as part of a certain lifestyle.

Most of the respondents (43.3%) agreed with the statement that they buy those fashion items which are endorsed by some celebrity/role model, while 3.3% and 33.3% boys are strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively with the same. Maximum percentage of the respondents, both girls and boys were agreed that they generally prefer fashion products which offer better quality in low price, while only 10% boys and 6.7% girls were not able to remark on it. According to Fringe (1999), consumers want the best product at the best price. Price is probably the most important consideration for an average consumer. The consumer must compare the total perceived worth of the aesthetic aspects of the garment or accessory with the retail price and his or her own budget.

43.3% of the girls and 36.7% boys always bought the products which are of their familiar brand even if there were other options available with similar features, but 16.7% girls and 6.7% boys wanted to endeavour other new brands also. Most of the respondents agreed to the fact that they try a new fashion product when it comes with some offer or on sale as it is more economical for the students. Girls (46.7%) agreed with the statement that high quality fashion products are at high price and 43.3% boys strongly agreed with this. Same trend was observed when 46.7% girls and 36.7% boys said that branded fashion products are symbol of socio-economic status. According to Khan (2006), consumers perceived price advertisement as reduction in price. Many advertisers project the regular price, as well as the offered price, showing a discount or a substantial saving. Reference price is the price compared with other products on sale. Other factors like product category, brand, initial price level, consumer group and retail outlet is also a matter of concern in price advertising.

It is further revealed that most of the students under study were glad to buy the fashion items which they saw in TV serials and movies. Fringe (1999), stated that fashion programmes on television are also an opportunity for designers to get publicity. TV events, such as the Academy Awards, also give exposure to the designer of the star. Many companies are aggressively campaigning to get their products placed in feature films and on the most popular TV shows. In their quest to link their clothing and accessories with the biggest names in

entertainment, they have to choose the appropriate film and celebrity to endorse their product and reach their target market.

CONCLUSION:

A fashion advertisement is a source of changing the attitudes of the consumers, so that it becomes favourable towards the company's products. Students are the main consumers of fashion products. College going students are more fashion conscious and always want to have recent and unique fashion trends. In this situation fashion advertisements play an important role influencing their fashion products buying behaviour.

The major findings of present study show that the fashion advertisements play a significant role in persuading students for buying particular fashion product. Results show that the most popular fashion advertising media among students were television, fashion magazines, women's magazines followed by internet and newspapers. Clothing, cosmetics and footwear were among fashion products for which students consider information supplied by different advertisements they see on television, different magazines, internet, newspapers and other fashion advertising media. It is evident from the study that students pay least attention to the advertisements of jewelry and so do not consider their advertisements for buying.

The study further shows that students pay more attention on some specific features of fashion advertisements which includes frequency of advertisements, presentation of advertisement with striking colours on glossy paper, advertisements theme, non verbal communication and model's chic. Other features which attract students were use of sentiments of target group, products with special offer and brand name of the products. The results further show that students like to buy those things which are used by their peer group, endorsed by some celebrity or which they see in TV serials and movies, while some boys strongly disagree with the same. Most of the students try a new product when it comes with some offer or on sale. But many students especially boys are not satisfied with the quality of the fashion products on sale. Boys also do not agree that high quality fashion products are always at high price.

Therefore, it can be concluded from the present study that fashion advertisements have great influence on the buying behaviour of the students. So this study can help the producers in marketing their fashion products through advertisements.

REFERENCES:

- Adorno, T. 1991. The Culture Industry, London: Routledge.
- Anonymous (2008) <http://www.lotsofessays.com/aup.php>. Fashion Advertisements, retrieved on 9.03.08.
- Anonymous (2008) www.marketresearch.com/product. retrieved on 9.03.08
- Craik, J. 1994. The Face of Fashion. Cultural Studies in Fashion, London: Routledge.
- Fringe, G.I. 1999. Fashion: From concept to consumer, 6th ed. Printice Hall of India Private Limited, New Delhi. 376pp.
- Goldman, 1992 Reading Ads Socially, London: Routledge.
- Hamburger, E. 1976. Fashion Business: Its All Yours. Canfield Press, Sanfrancisco. 306pp.
- Khan, M., 2006. Consumer Behaviour 2ND ed., New Age International Publishers, New Delhi. 229pp.
- Kotler, P. and Keller, K.L. 2006. Marketing Management. 12th ed. Prentice Hall of India Private Limited, New Delhi. 729pp.
- Loudon, D.L. and Bitta, A.J.D. 2006. Consumer Behaviour : Concepts anf application, 4th ed, TATA-Mcgraw Hills Publishing Company Limited, New Delhi. 788pp.

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